

Polarographic Study of Ternary Complexes in Solution : Complex Formation Between Copper(II) 2,2'-bipyridyl 1 : 1 Complex and Ligands Containing Oxygen and/or Nitrogen Donor Atoms as Secondary Ligands

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Electrode behaviour of some mixed-ligand complexes of Cu(II) with 2,2'-bipyridyl as primary ligand and some aliphatic, aromatic and amino acids and phenols as secondary ligands have been studied in aqueous potassium nitrate. All the complexes are observed to undergo diffusion controlled, single-step, two electron irreversible electro-reduction at dme. The study has been made at three different temperatures namely 30, 35 and 40° and at the varying ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 1 for the metal : (primary ligand) : (secondary ligand). Besides half wave potentials, $E_{1/2}$, the formal rate constant, k_f , the activation energy of rearrangement of the depolarizer, Q_e , the activation energy of diffusion, Q_D have been calculated for each system. It is observed that all the complexes follow a particular reaction mechanism with temperature and the half-wave potential shifts towards more positive side with rise of temperature indicating easier reduction. With the exception of the complexes with aromatic acids and catechol. Factors for this behaviour have been observed. The driving forces for the formation of ternary systems have been analysed. Discriminating nature of the parent 2,2'-bipyridyl complex towards incoming secondary ligands has been discussed.

THE present heightened interest in the solution chemistry of ternary complexes¹⁻⁷ of biologically important metal ions stems out of the consideration that mixed chelation occurs commonly in biological fluids as a large variety of potential ligands are likely to compete for metal ions found *in vivo*⁸. It is well known that ternary complexes play an important role in biological process. Ternary complexes containing Cu(II)⁹⁻¹¹ as a metal ion are relatively well investigated because copper is a very important element essential to the healthy life of plants¹²⁻¹⁵ and animals¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

Many potentiometric determinations during the last decade have been directed to reveal driving forces of the ternary complexes giving importance to electronic effects (π systems of the ligands) besides coulombic effects (neutralization of charge in ternary complexes) and lower steric hindrance compared with corresponding binary *bis*-complexes²⁰. A general impression appears to have gained ground that these mixed-ligand complexes would be more stable than one would expect for purely statistical reasons. Sigel and coworkers have further been able to hint at the discriminating qualities of Cu²⁺-2,2'-bipyridyl, 1 : 1 complex towards the second ligand to be coordinated. Polarographic studies, though expected to furnish more exact information on factors like electronic effects, have been used much less due to obvious difficulties in applying the technique to these systems.

Considering that the electrode behaviour is a characteristic property of coordination compounds²¹ and further considering that the dynamic character of polarography has been used in recent years²² to express the reactivity and kinetic properties of such compounds, the present study is an attempt to gather facts leading to a better understanding²³ of the electrode behaviour of these ternary complexes at the dropping mercury electrode in general.

The system chosen for the present study involves 2, 2'-bipyridyl as a primary ligand and a number of O or O ; N and N donors. All the polarographic characteristics have been determined under the assumption that the complex formation between Cu²⁺-2,2'-bipyridyl-ligand is complete. This assumption is reasonable and it is confirmed by Sigel²⁰. The secondary ligands taken for study are : ethylenediamine (en), NH₂CH₂CH₂NH₂, a N-donor, amino acids [glycine (Gly) NH₂CH₂COOH, valine (Val) (CH₃)₂CH CH NH₂COOH, serine (Ser) HO CH₂CH(NH₂) COOH, leucine (Leu) (CH₃)₂CH CH₂CH (NH₂) COOH] all N-O donors, aliphatic acids [formic acid (For) HCOOH, oxalic acid (Ox) (COOH)₂, tartaric acid (Tar) (CH OH COOH)₂, citric acid (Cit) (CH₂COOH)₂ C(OH) COOH, succinic acid (Suc) (CH₂COOH)₂] aromatic acids [benzoic acid (Ben) C₆H₅COOH, phthalic acid (Ph) C₆H₄(COOH)₂, salicylic acid (Sal) C₆H₄OH COOH, mandelic acid (Man) C₆H₅(CHOH)₂, gallic acid (Gal) C₆H₃(OH)₃COOH] and phenols

[resorcinol (Res) $C_6H_4(OH)_2$, catechol (Cat) $C_6H_4(OH)_2$] all O-donors.

Experimental

All studies were made in double-distilled water and fresh solutions of the ligands were prepared when needed. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Twenty ml of reaction mixture (depolarizer + supporting electrolyte + maximum suppressor + solvent) were always taken in the polarographic cell, care being taken to keep the supporting electrolyte concentration constant. Polarographic measurements were made with a manual polarographic circuit recommended by Kolthoff and Lingane²⁴. All potentials were measured against a Hume and Harris saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Other experimental details have been described elsewhere²⁵. Resistance of the system was measured by an ac wheatstone bridge. The resistance was found to be between 700-800 Ω .

The characteristics of the dropping mercury electrode (open circuit) were determined for at least three heights. One such set is given below :

$$h = 30 \text{ cm}, m = 1.85 \text{ mgs}^{-1}, t = 4.1 \text{ sec.}$$

$$m^{2/3} = t^{1/6} = 1.877 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$$

The systems studied are [Cu(bip)L] in the ratios 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 1 at temperatures 30, 35 and 40°.

Results

Tables 1 and 2 contain the polarographic characteristics of the system [Cu(bip)L] in the ratios of

1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 1 in 0.5M KNO_3 aqueous solution. The morphology of curves show single well-defined waves at dme for all the cases except in the cases [Cu(bip)Gal], [Cu(bip)Leu] and [Cu(bip)Cat], in which two step reduction wave is obtained. Perusal of the $E_{1/2}$ values for these systems lead to

the conclusion that [Cu(bip)] 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 binary complex is difficult to reduce than the ternary aliphatic and aromatic acids complexes except the complex [Cu(bip)Ox] and [Cu(bip)Ben] but the ternary complexes of amino acids are more stable. The values of formal rate constants also support the same results. The slope values calculated by the "log-plot" (Oldhan and Parry) E vs $\log(5.5-x)/x/5(1-x)$ indicate that all the complexes undergo irreversible electro-reduction in aqueous solution as the values of the slope are greater in each case than the theoretical value of 0.029 v. The values of half-wave potentials $E_{1/2}$ are also calculated by the 'log-plot' given above. The value of number of electrons transferred 'n' calculated by Ilkovic equation was nearly equal to two for each of the complexes except in case of complexes involving gallic acid, leucine and catechol in which the value of 'n' is about one for both waves. Values of diffusion current $i_d(\mu a)$ are directly taken from the polarographic waves. Formal potentials have been determined experimentally vs SCE. Rate constants (K_f) are calculated with the help of formal potential. The diffusion controlled nature of the polarographic waves was determined by varying the height of mercury column and studying the corresponding change in diffusion currents. The constancy of $i_d/h^{1/2}$

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Cu(II)

Complex	h=40 cm		(1 : 1 : 1) Temp. 35°		KNO ₃ =0.5M		Formal rate constant 'K _f ' cm sec ⁻¹ 1 × 10 ⁻⁴
	E _{1/2} Volt vs SCE	Slope (Volts)	Diffusion current i _d (μa)	Transfer coefficient ' α '	Diffusion coefficient 'D' cm ² /sec 1 × 10 ⁻⁶	Formal potential vs SCE at 35°	
Cu : bip	-0.1065	0.0720	0.6540	0.3900	0.0549 × 10 ⁻¹	+0.020	0.1557 × 10 ⁻¹
Cu : bip : For	-0.0980	0.1050	1.0100	0.2632	0.1303	-0.056	1.6420
Cu : bip : Ox	-0.1100	0.1800	1.2400	0.1667	0.1973	-0.048	1.5620
Cu : bip : Tar	-0.0970	0.0930	1.0000	0.2565	0.1309	-0.064	1.6720
Cu : bip : Cit	-0.0920	0.1150	1.1000	0.2269	0.1539	-0.069	1.7950
Cu : bip : Suc	-0.0920	0.1260	1.0800	0.2341	0.1497	-0.058	1.7480
Cu : bip : Ben	-0.1100	0.1510	1.0100	0.1821	0.1309	-0.050	1.4080
Cu : bip : Ph	-0.1000	0.1410	1.0500	0.2034	0.1416	-0.060	1.5760
Cu : bip : Sal	-0.0880	0.0920	1.0000	0.2950	0.1237	-0.047	1.6460
Cu : bip : Man	-0.0900	0.1030	1.0200	0.2680	0.1054	-0.072	1.5660
Cu : bip : Gal	-0.0530	0.0720	0.6700	0.3990	0.0576 × 10 ⁻¹	-0.054	1.1180
	-0.2800	0.0620	0.2600	0.4610	0.0086 × 10 ⁻²		0.2680 × 10 ⁻¹
Cu : bip : Gly	-0.1070	0.1670	1.0600	0.1799	0.1442	-0.081	1.4160
Cu : bip : Val	-0.1490	0.2800	1.1600	0.0925	0.1728	-0.018	1.0100
Cu : bip : Ser	-0.1150	0.1450	1.0800	0.1639	0.1497	-0.064	1.4530
Cu : bip : Leu	-0.0105	0.0270	0.5100	2.0840	0.0833 × 10 ⁻¹		1.1820
	-0.3150	0.1410	0.5000	0.5320	0.0326 × 10 ⁻¹	-0.0385	0.4786 × 10 ⁻¹
Cu : bip : Res	-0.0975	0.1370	0.0900	0.2100	0.2416	-0.035	1.9950
Cu : bip : Cat	-0.0880	0.0750	0.6700	0.7400	0.0576		1.0580
	-0.2880	0.0830	0.2900	0.7090	0.0107 × 10 ⁻¹	-0.0	0.2270 × 10 ⁻¹
Cu : bip : En	-0.1068	0.2670	1.5500	0.2284	0.3088	-0.06	1.421

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Cu(II)
(1 : 2 : 1)
Temp. = 35°

Complex	h=40 cm E _{1/2} Volt vs SCE	Slope (Volts)	Diffusion current i _d (µA)	Transfer coefficient 'α'	Diffusion coefficient 'D' cm ² /sec 1 × 10 ⁻⁶	KNO ₃ = 0.5M Formal potential vs SCE at 35°	Formal rate constant 'K _f ' cm sec ⁻¹ 1 × 10 ⁻⁴
Cu bip	-0.2000	0.2680	1.1100	0.1070	0.1553	-0.065	0.5679 × 10 ⁻¹
Cu bip . For	-0.1420	0.0890	0.8900	0.3162	0.1016	-0.095	1.5030
Cu : bip Ox	-0.2000	0.2000	1.0000	0.1829	0.1283	-0.100	1.0920
Cu : bip Tar	-0.1780	0.1150	0.7800	0.2611	0.0515 × 10 ⁻¹	-0.100	0.9310
Cu : bip Cit	-0.1600	0.1180	1.0000	0.1109	0.1283	-0.125	1.1590
Cu : bip Suc	-0.1620	0.1310	1.0000	0.1766	0.1283	-0.100	1.8850
Cu . bip Ben	-0.2000	0.2800	0.7200	0.0983	0.0665 × 10 ⁻¹	-0.150	0.7621 × 10 ⁻¹
Cu : bip Ph	-0.1600	0.1140	0.9100	0.2860	0.1063	-0.101	1.3730
Cu . bip Sal	-0.1360	0.1000	0.8200	0.3010	0.1086	-0.101	1.5730
Cu : bip Man	-0.1440	0.0860	0.9200	0.2810	0.0863 × 10 ⁻¹	-0.133	4.5900
Cu . bip Gal	-0.2120	0.1800	0.9320	0.2660	0.1594	-0.125	1.0360
Cu : bip Gly	-0.2570	0.1920	1.0100	0.1379	0.1309	-0.145	1.1140
Cu : bip Val	-0.2650	0.1850	1.0300	0.1595	0.1309	-0.169	1.2620
Cu : bip Ser	-0.2600	0.1450	1.0100	0.1993	0.1361	-0.103	1.1680
Cu : bip Leu	-0.2420	0.2150	1.0600	0.1245	0.1442	-0.162	1.1690
Cu : bip Res	-0.1840	0.1600	1.0800	0.1800	0.1497	-0.134	1.5330
Cu bip Cat	-0.1100	0.0600	0.4400	0.9200	0.0248 × 10 ⁻¹	-0.133	0.9298 × 10 ⁻¹
	-0.4050	0.0670	0.3600	0.7300	0.0166 × 10 ⁻¹		0.3710 × 10 ⁻¹
Cu : bip En	-0.2210	0.2000	1.5500	0.2990	0.3083	-0.060	1.4210

values show that the process is diffusion controlled. Higher values of diffusion currents, i_d in case of ternary complexes are observed in comparison to the binary [Cu(bip)] 1 1 and 1 2 system, because the chelation makes the depolarizer smaller than [Cu(bip)] complex. Amongst the chelates so formed, the ternary complexes of oxalic acid, benzoic acid and valine are smaller than those of the other acids and provide the highest value of diffusion current in each series. The observed values of diffusion coefficients 'D' support this argument. The values of $E_{1/2}$ for the complexes are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The activation energy, Q_a , and the activation energy of the diffusion, Q_D , have been calculated using the following given by Vlček²⁵

$$\log \frac{i_d - 1}{1} = -\log A' + \frac{Q_a - \frac{1}{2} Q_D}{2.3 RT} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{and } \log \frac{i_d}{m^{2/3} t^{1/6}} = \log 0.67 n F C D_{1/3} - \frac{\frac{1}{2} Q_D}{2.3 RT} \quad (2)$$

where symbols have their usual meanings. The data on activation energy of diffusion and rearrangement of the Cu(II) bip complexes [Cu(bip)L] with secondary ligands are given in Table 4. The plots of half-wave potential vs temperature (Figs 1-4) are found to be straight lines. It may therefore be concluded²⁷ that the electroreduction of these complexes follows a particular reaction mechanism with temperature. It has been observed that for all the complexes, the value of diffusion current i_d increases and that of half wave potential $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more positive values with the increase of temperature indicating easier reduction^{28, 29}. However in the case of [Cu(bip)cat], [Cu(bip) aromatic acids], the $E_{1/2}$ values become more negative with the rise

 TABLE 4—ACTIVATION ENERGY 'Q_a' AND ACTIVATION ENERGY OF DIFFUSION 'Q_D' OF Cu(II)BIPYRIDYL MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

Complexes	1 1 1		1 2 1	
	Q _D (Kcal)	Q _a (Kcal)	Q _D (Kcal)	Q _a (Kcal)
Cu bip	9.2575	6.7780	7.8924	10.2100
Cu bip Form	2.3257	5.8230	7.0034	9.2164
Cu bip Ox	9.8221	6.2751	7.3210	10.1275
Cu bip Tar	1.8474	5.5200	6.8080	8.0040
Cu . bip Cit	1.7423	5.5620	6.5670	7.8766
Cu bip Suc	1.5253	5.5525	6.1240	7.7777
Cu . bip Ben	3.2810	7.1230	9.5230	11.2251
Cu bip Ph	2.1436	6.7273	9.2000	10.7180
Cu bip Sal	1.5232	5.7034	8.7200	10.2135
Cu bip Man	1.8236	5.7100	8.5120	9.2375
Cu bip Gal	2.3236	5.8234	6.2310	9.0201
Cu bip Gly	6.8	9.7980	9.2	12.2390
Cu bip Ser	7.8	9.8300	9.7	12.5670
Cu bip . Val	8.5	10.2345	9.8	13.9520
Cu . bip Leu	6.65	8.6285	8.5	11.3610
Cu . bip Res	2.102	5.7352	6.9278	10.8005
Cu : bip Cat	—	—	7.8231	10.8752
Cu bip En	9.752	23.276	10.235	25.2100

of temperature. This is probably because of decreased adsorption of catechol and aromatic acids at higher temperature (Figs. 5a and b). The current potential curves for these complexes are well-defined waves at all temperatures (30, 35, 40°). The diffusion current values for all these complexes increase with the rise in temperature. The transfer coefficient α increases with temperature indicating that the electroreduction process becomes more and more reversible at higher temperature (Table 3). The values of activation energy increase within the series with increase in the value of half-wave potential. The activation energy of [Cu(bip)cat] 1 1 1 cannot be calculated because the dependence of $i_d - 1/i$ vs T^{-1} is not linear due to its adsorption nature. Such a behaviour indicates complicated course of the electrode reaction²⁶.

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on half wave potential of Cu: bip . aliphatic acids (1 : 1 : 1 —) (1 : 2 : 1 - - -).

Discussion

Among the mixed-ligand complexes of aliphatic acids series, the complex, $[Cu(bip)Ox]$, seems to be the most stable in comparison with others. There are several factors governing the stability of a complex, whether simple or mixed, like statistical factors, geometry of the mixed complex, steric factors (size of the ligand), size and charge on metal ion, charge on ligands, etc. All the factors being the same, the stability of the mixed-ligand

complexes in this series can be expected to follow the order of size of the secondary ligand, namely oxalic acid < tartaric acid < succinic acid < citric acid. The complex involving a monodentate and less charged ligand like formic acid should be less stable than other complexes of the series. In the series $[Cu(bip)$ aromatic acids], the complex $[Cu(bip) Ben]$ seems to be the most stable. Benzoic acid has the smallest size in the series, but it is also a monodentate ligand. However, the presence of the aromatic ring^{30,31} alters bonding properties of this

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on half wave potential of Cu : bip : aromatic acids (1 : 1 : 1 —) (1 : 2 : 1 ---)

carboxylic acid if compared with the formic acid. Among complexes involving amino acids as secondary ligands the [Cu(bip)Val] complex is the most stable. The half-wave potentials shift towards more negative values in the series [Cu(bip)Gly] < [Cu(bip)Ser] < [Cu(bip)Val] and the rate constant decreases. This means that the ease of reduction decreases or the rate of

electron transfer decreases in this series of complexes. Available stability constant data also support the same trend^{22,23}. In the series the stability constant being highest for the complex [Cu(bip)Val] which may indicate^{21,24-27} that here the electron density around the central metal ion is also comparatively high and this would render acceptance of the two incoming electrons

Fig. 8. Effect of temperature on half wave potential of Cu : bp : amino acids (1 : 1 : 1 —) (1 : 2 : 1 - - - -)

(from the electrode) in the metal orbital more difficult giving more negative value of $E_{1/2}$ as compared to other complexes.

The values of half-wave potential (Table 3) show a trend of shifting towards more positive potential with rise of temperature (except in the case of aromatic acids and catechol which show kinetically catalytically controlled nature)²⁸ indicating easier reduction and increased degree of reversibility^{28,29}. According to Glasstone⁴⁰, this easier reduction may be due to decrease of over-voltage with the rise of temperature, which may

further be understood on the basis of thermal agitation of the diffusion layer and that of diffuse double-layer which may result in decreasing the compactness of the depolarizer to the electrode surface. Another factor which may also contribute to the easier reduction of the depolarizer depends on the energy of the electrons in the electrode. Considering that the transfer of electrons from electrode to the depolarizer would take place without any loss of energy (Franck-Condon principle), a primary condition for a given reaction velocity³⁴ is that there should be suitable energy

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on half wave potential of Cu : bip : phenols (1 : 1 : 1 —) (1 : 2 : 1 - - - -)

Fig. 5a. Electrocapillary curves for some aromatic acids

Fig. 5b. Electrocapillary curve for [Cu(bip)pyrocate].

level in the electrode as compared to the energy of the empty lowest lying available orbitals in the depolarizer. It should be noted that transferable electrons⁴¹ are the electrons populating the Fermi level. This implies that any process which either increases the energy of the electrons to the Fermi-level in the electrode or makes easier the availability of empty orbital in the depolarizer, will facilitate the electron transfer. Increase of temperature is one such process which may, on the one-hand, increase the energy of the electrons in the electrode that may reach the Fermi-level and on the other hand, facilitate the rearrangement of the electronic configuration of the depolarizer and hence increase the availability of redox orbital on the depolarizer.

Increase of diffusion current value with rise of temperature in the reduction of complexes at dme is attributed to the increased concentration of the

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Cu(II)-BIPYRIDYL MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Complexes	T°C	h=40 cm			KNO ₃ =0.5M		
		1:1:1			1:2:1		
		E _{1/2} (V vs SCE)	i _d (μa)	α	E _{1/2} (V vs SCE)	i _d (μa)	α
Cu : bip : For	30	-0.1115	0.9840	0.2602	-0.1488	0.8020	0.3222
	35	-0.0980	1.0100	0.2632	-0.1420	0.8900	0.3162
	40	-0.0955	1.1100	0.2730	-0.1382	0.9520	0.3070
Cu : bip : Ox	30	-0.1372	1.2000	0.1582	-0.2375	0.9726	0.1462
	35	-0.1100	1.2400	0.1667	-0.2000	1.0000	0.1829
	40	-0.1070	1.3120	0.1720	-0.1925	1.0856	0.1298
Cu : bip : Tar	30	-0.1050	0.9950	0.2201	-0.1805	0.6950	0.2707
	35	-0.0970	1.0000	0.2565	-0.1730	0.7800	0.2611
	40	-0.0925	1.0922	0.2623	-0.1710	0.8920	0.2589
Cu : bip : Cit	30	-0.1000	0.9870	0.2129	-0.1635	0.9620	0.1112
	35	-0.0920	1.0000	0.2269	-0.1600	1.0000	0.1109
	40	-0.0900	1.1200	0.2369	-0.1585	1.1213	0.1000
Cu : bip : Suc	30	-0.1100	0.9950	0.2212	-0.1685	0.9821	0.1820
	35	-0.0920	1.0800	0.2341	-0.1620	1.0000	0.1756
	40	-0.0890	1.1022	0.2398	-0.1575	1.0999	0.1725
Cu : bip : Ben	30	-0.1004	0.0100	0.1803	-0.1885	0.7115	0.0980
	35	-0.1100	0.0100	0.1821	-0.2000	0.7300	0.0983
	40	-0.1222	0.0332	0.1870	-0.2175	0.7396	1.0232
Cu : bip : Ph	30	-0.0904	1.0320	0.2005	-0.1475	0.8700	0.2350
	35	-0.1000	1.0500	0.2034	-0.1600	0.9100	0.2360
	40	-0.1098	1.0778	0.2124	-0.1720	0.9445	0.2389
Cu : bip : Sal	30	-0.0802	0.0982	0.2910	-0.1250	0.8175	0.2820
	35	-0.0880	1.0000	0.2950	-0.1360	0.8200	0.3010
	40	-0.0952	1.0555	0.2975	-0.1487	0.8240	0.3120
Cu : bip : Man	30	-0.0820	1.0022	0.2635	-0.1415	0.9155	0.2775
	35	-0.0900	1.0200	0.2680	-0.1500	0.9200	0.2810
	40	-0.1005	1.0532	0.2705	-0.1685	0.9235	0.2890
Cu : bip : Gal	30	-0.0480	0.6625	0.3982	-0.1898	0.8120	0.2600
		-0.2790	0.2535	0.4690			
	35	-0.0590	0.6700	0.3990	-0.2120	0.8970	0.2660
		-0.2800	0.2600	0.4610			
	40	-0.0715	0.6730	0.3998	-0.2145	0.9395	0.2715
		-0.2825	0.2625	0.4600			
Cu : bip : Gly	30	-0.1200	1.0050	0.1742	-0.2789	1.0025	0.1285
	35	-0.1070	1.0600	0.1799	-0.2570	1.0100	0.1379
	40	-0.0825	1.1011	0.1822	-0.2355	1.0225	0.1394
Cu : bip : Ser	30	-0.1295	1.0332	0.1615	-0.2825	1.0075	0.1973
	35	-0.1150	1.0900	0.1689	-0.2600	1.0100	0.1993
	40	-0.1015	1.1000	0.1664	-0.2385	1.0375	0.2015
Cu : bip : Val	30	-0.1615	1.1025	0.0910	-0.2875	1.0225	0.1545
	35	-0.1490	1.1600	0.0925	-0.2650	1.0300	0.1595
	40	-0.1400	1.1885	0.1200	-0.2600	1.0375	0.1615
Cu : bip : Leu	30	-0.0080	0.5050	2.0000	-0.2580	1.0553	0.1200
		-0.3575	0.4920	0.5420			
	35	-0.0105	0.5100	2.0340	-0.2420	1.0600	0.1245
		-0.3150	0.5000	0.5320			
	40	-0.0118	0.5150	2.2525	-0.2200	1.0985	0.1273
		-0.2933	0.5120	0.5315			
Cu : bip : Res	30	-0.0992	1.0775	0.2000	-0.1875	1.0532	0.1695
	35	-0.0975	1.0900	0.2100	-0.1840	1.0800	0.1800
	40	-0.0890	1.2700	0.2400	-0.1800	1.1032	0.1825
Cu : bip : Cal	30	-0.0915	0.6000	0.7332	-0.1085	0.4225	0.9117
		-0.3775	0.2815	0.7225	-0.4000	0.3515	0.7375
	35	-0.0880	0.6700	0.7400	-0.1100	0.4400	0.9200
		-0.3880	0.2900	0.7000	-0.4050	0.3600	0.7300
	40	-0.0825	0.6975	0.7495	-0.1135	0.4475	0.9265
		-0.3915	0.3085	0.6925	-0.4115	0.3675	0.7239
Cu : bip : En	30	-0.2000	1.29	0.2170	-0.2070	1.2900	0.2684
	35	-0.1068	1.55	0.2284	-0.2210	1.5500	0.2990
	40	-0.1060	1.60	0.2637	-0.2530	1.6000	0.2950

TABLE 5—HALF WAVE POTENTIALS OF Cu : bip : AMINO ACIDS (O AND N DONOR) AND Cu : bip : ETHYLENEDIAMINE (N DONOR LIGAND), Cu : bip : ALIPHATIC ACIDS (OXYGEN DONOR), Cu : bip : AROMATIC ACIDS (OXYGEN DONOR) AND Cu : bip : PHENOLS (OXYGEN DONOR)
 $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of Cu, bip (1 : 1) = 0.1065

Secondary Ligands	I $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ CuL	II $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ Cu(bip)L	III [Cu(bip)L]- [Cubip]	IV [Cu(bip)L]- [CuL]	V [Cu(bip)L-Cu(bip)]-CuL $\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$
<i>Cu . bip . Amino Acids (O and N donor) and Cu . bip : ethylenediamine (N donor ligand)</i>					
Ethylenediamine	-0.02	-0.1068	-0.0090	-0.0868	+0.027
Glycine	+0.005	-0.1070	-0.0005	-0.1020	-0.0045
Valine	+0.028	-0.1490	-0.0425	-0.1210	-0.0145
Serine	+0.017	-0.1150	-0.0085	-0.1080	0.0085
Leucine	-0.20	-0.3150	-0.2085	-0.1150	-0.0085
<i>Cu . bip . Aliphatic Acids (Oxygen donor)</i>					
Formic acid	+0.020	-0.098	+0.0035	-0.078	-0.0115
Oxalic acid	+0.015	-0.110	+0.0095	-0.095	-0.0115
Tartaric acid	+0.020	-0.097	+0.0095	-0.077	-0.0105
Citric acid	+0.025	-0.092	+0.0145	-0.087	-0.0105
Succinic acid	+0.027	-0.032	+0.0145	-0.065	-0.0115
<i>Cu : bip : Aromatic Acids (Oxygen donor)</i>					
Benzoic acid	+0.018	-0.1100	-0.0035	-0.092	-0.0145
Phthalic acid	+0.022	-0.1000	+0.0065	-0.078	-0.0155
Salicylic acid	+0.030	-0.0880	+0.0185	-0.0580	-0.0115
Mandelic acid	+0.028	-0.0900	+0.0165	-0.0620	-0.0115
Gallic acid	+0.020	-0.0535	-0.0530	-0.0335	-0.0330
<i>Cu : bip : Phenols (Oxygen donor)</i>					
Resorcinol	+0.020	-0.0975	+0.0090	-0.0775	-0.0110
Catechol	-0.270	-0.3880	-0.2815	-0.1180	-0.0115

depolarizer at the electrode surface and increased rate of charge transfer. Data on activation energy show that it decreases with decrease of half-wave potential indicating an easier reduction. Reduction is regarded as comprising the acceptance of an electron into the lowest unoccupied, or singly occupied orbital of the depolarizer. If the orbital has a high electron affinity, a slight change in configuration will take place for the direct reaction of the depolarizer particle with electrode. A large amount of energy of rearrangement will be necessary if the orbital has a low electron affinity since direct reduction in this instance would require a very large negative applied potential, so the activation energy is proportional to the half-wave potential of the complexes.

To observe the discriminating power of 2,2'-bipyridyl complex towards various secondary ligands the effects of different ligands competing in the complex formation and the shift of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values have been separated by taking the difference of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for [Cu(bip)L] and [CuL], the $\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, [Cu(bip)L - Cu(bip)] - (CuL) being calculated as difference of the values of column III and I of Table 5.

For the 2,2' bip-Cu²⁺-en system, a positive $\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ value is observed. In agreement with the results the value of $\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for the mixed O, N ligand, i.e. amino acids, the values are in between those found for O, O and N ligand. The observation of

a positive $\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ value would mean that the ligand under consideration forms a more stable complex with the free (hydrated) Cu²⁺ ion than with the Cu²⁺-2,2'-bip 1 : 1 complex. However it does not mean that no ternary complex is formed in solutions containing equimolar mixtures of two different ligands and Cu²⁺. Thus Cu²⁺-2,2'-bip 1 : 1 complex seems to possess discriminating qualities towards other ligands, preferably coordinating 'O' containing ligand and the resulting ternary complexes being remarkably stable. The ligand 2,2'-bipyridyl induces a stronger field at the Cu²⁺ ion and it is bound to Cu²⁺ through a donor bond but it is also a π acceptor (π bonds : back donation), hence the resulting charge on the Cu²⁺ ion in the 1 : 1 complex is higher with 2,2'-bipyridyl. Thus distorted octahedral Cu(H₂O)₆²⁺ ion will be somewhat more strongly distorted towards a square-planar coordination sphere by the coordination of 2,2'-bip., creating the right geometry for the coordination of the second ligand, which will be especially favoured due to negatively charged donor oxygen atoms. Also the π system of the O-ligand seems also to have some (but a smaller) effect. This suggests that in complexes like 2,2'-bip-Cu²⁺-phenols, a cooperative effect may occur between the π systems of the two ligands bound to the same Cu²⁺. In line with this assumption are results obtained for several ternary 2,2'-bip-Cu²⁺-carboxylate complexes. The aromatic acid anions form somewhat more stable complexes with the Cu²⁺-2,2'-bip 1 : 1 complex than aliphatic carboxylic acid anions^{4a}.

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